

METHODS OF APPLYING MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the article, it is necessary to adequately prepare and educate our youth who will create our future in the rapidly developing era. with the concept of modernity, integrally connecting the characteristics of humanity, changing teaching methods, educational goals, The new generation, built on the basis of the approach based on pedagogical technologies, is experiencing a difficult period related to the development of the state education standard. the goal of productive use of innovations and ped-techniques in education is envisaged.

Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 is intended for the years 2022-2026. The development strategy of New Uzbekistan in this strategy envisages the creation of modern innovative pedagogical technologies in education, the use of pedagogical technologies in working with students and young people, and as a result of this, training students as mature staff who are masters of their profession.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PF-5712 development of modern pedagogical technologies, improvement of the education system for children with special educational needs and the use of modern pedagogical technologies in education to improve the quality of educational services provided to them.

Today, in modern educational conditions, teaching methods are experiencing a difficult period related to the change of educational goals, the development of a new generation state education standard based on the approach based on the concept. If we do not take into account their interests and young characteristics, they will remain wrapped in their shells. In order to avoid such problems, every pedagogue needs to work hard on himself and to prepare for each lesson and bring news of interest to them.

It was not for nothing that our honorable president recognized 2023 as the year of human attention and quality education. When working with our students and young people, we pedagogues should treat them in a friendly manner, share their opinions, study their inner world

and deal with each young person separately. Technology is a Greek word, meaning "technos" - art, skill, "logos" - teaching. In the history of the formation and development of the concept of pedagogical technology, there were different views: it is a teaching about technical tools, and it is interpreted as consistent and regular organization of the teaching process. Currently, there are several definitions of pedagogical technologies.

"pedagogical technology" can be expressed in three forms.

1. scientific: pedagogical technologies - the part of pedagogical science that studies and develops the goals, contents and methods of teaching and designs pedagogical processes;
2. procedural-descriptive: description (algorithm) of the process of achieving the planned educational results,
3. a set of goals, content, methods and tools; Procedurally efficient: technological implementation (pedagogical) process, operation of all personal, instrumental and methodological pedagogical tools.

"Pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical techniques, a special collection of forms, methods, methods, teaching methods, educational tools. At the same time, it also means the organizational-methodical factor of the pedagogical process.

Innovative technologies - teaching methods aimed at achieving a positive result due to dynamic changes in the child's personal development in modern socio-cultural conditions, system of educational tools. Pedagogical innovations can change or improve educational processes. Innovative technologies combine advanced creative technologies and stereotypical elements of education, which have proven their effectiveness in the process of pedagogical activity.

Initial theoretical positions of project-based education:

1. The main attention is paid to the student, his abilities help to develop creatively;
2. The educational process is not based on science logic; and in the logic of activities that have a personal meaning for the student, which increases his motivation for education;
3. The individual pace of work on the project provides a way out to the level of development of each student;
4. An integrated approach to the development of educational projects helps to develop the basic physiological and mental balanced functions of students;
5. Deep, conscious mastering of basic knowledge is ensured due to its universal use in various situations.

One of the wise men says about the main rule of success: "You should work every day as if you were placed on the scales. Do what you are told to do, and you will get more. Know that the most popular way to achieve success is to work hard." Formation and development of science and educational knowledge and skills in the process of active multi-level cognitive activity of students in an emotionally comfortable environment with modern technologies, allows to develop positive motivation for learning.

At the current stage, the concept of modern pedagogical technologies is actively used in pedagogical practice in student and youth education. However, there are great differences in its understanding and application, as well as many definitions given by different scholars. For example, B. T. Likhachev, V. P. Bepalko, I. P. Volkov, understanding is a meaningful generalization of pedagogical technology that incorporates the meanings of all definitions.

The main stage of preparation for training sessions is the planning of the training process. These process steps include:

1. Determining the purpose and result of the lesson.
2. Development of control assignments and evaluation criteria.
3. Selection of educational resources.
4. Determining the teaching and learning strategy.
5. Choose the type of lesson.
6. Development of a technological map of the lesson.

One of the important aspects of the lesson for the student is the understanding of the need for personal interest in learning, so that students not only in the result, rather, they can feel their competence during the entire educational process. The influence of education on the development of the student's personality. Therefore, a modern lesson should be built on a combination of specially organized activities and simple interpersonal relationships. therefore, the age and psychological characteristics of students are taken into account through a personal communication plan in the lesson. The concept of pedagogical technology of a specific subject and local level is almost completely covered by the concept of teaching methodology; the difference between them lies only in the placement of accents, In technologies, procedural, quantitative and computational components are more expressed, in methods - purpose, content, quality and change-oriented aspects. Technology differs from methods by its reproducibility, stability of results, lack of many "ifs". Mixing of technologies and methods sometimes leads to methods being part of technologies, sometimes, on the contrary, certain technologies are part of teaching methods.

Modern educational technologies include:

- Project teaching methods;
- The technology of using game methods in teaching: role-playing, business, didactic, interactive crosswords, test with assessment and other types of educational games;
- Teaching cooperation (team, group work).
- Problem-based educational technology and others.

Having a pedagogical technology gives the teacher the opportunity to organize the pedagogical effect according to his main goal. Transferring the child to the position of the subject. The level of mastering pedagogical technology can be elementary and professional. Play is the spark that ignites the flame of inquisitiveness and curiosity.

I think it is very important for students to use game technology because it is a tool that provides: Game technologies. Moral qualities of a person are formed in games, especially team games. K. D. Ushinsky wrote: The longer you protect the child from serious affairs, the harder it will be for him to move. It is the task of education to make serious activities interesting for a child. Game technology is built as a holistic education, covers a certain part of the educational process and is combined with the general content, plot, character. The educational goal of the game is to develop independence, naturalization of the will, cooperation in the formation of certain approaches, points of view, spiritual, aesthetic and worldview, collectivism, the ability to join a team, and communication skills.

Games that develop activity are aimed at developing attention, memory, speech, thinking, comparison skills, matching, finding similarities, hypothesis, imagination, creative

ability, empathy, reflection, finding the optimal solution, motivating educational activities. Nowadays, there is a lot of knowledge, and the methods of acquiring it are also radically changing based on the requirements of time and space. but also great changes are taking place in the methods of learning new knowledge. At the same time that the modernization of the education system is being carried out in our republic, a new content, approach, and pedagogical mentality are being proposed. Strengthening the student's interest in knowledge independently with a creative approach to each issue; always organizing the cooperative activities of the pedagogue and the student. The main basis of pedagogical technology depends on the chosen technologies for the cooperation of the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal.

Every educational technology used to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal set in the teaching process can organize cooperative activities between the teacher and the student. if both of them can achieve a positive result, if students can think independently, work creatively, search, analyze, draw their own conclusions, evaluate themselves, the group, and the group, and the teacher can be effective only if he can create opportunities and conditions for such activities. As long as life goes on, education and upbringing are rapidly developing, ped-technologies keep changing and updating according to new requirements.

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